

Studies on Donor Ability of μ -Oxobis(tri-n-butyltin) towards Cobalt(II) and Nickel(II)

A. K. SRIVASTAVA and MAHESH SRIVASTAVA

Department of Chemistry, Meerut College, Meerut-250 001

and

R. K. AGARWAL

Department of Chemistry, L. R. Post Graduate College, Sahibabad

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Cobalt(II) and nickel(II) compounds of μ -oxobis(tri-n-butyltin) (TBTO) have been synthesised and characterised on the basis of analytical data, magnetic susceptibility, infrared and electronic spectra.

OXO-organotin(IV) compounds $R_3-Sn-O-Sn-R_3$ (R =propyl, butyl or phenyl), are basic in nature¹ and form addition compounds with Lewis acids². Paul *et al.*³ have recently synthesised the addition compounds of Sn^{IV} , Ti^{IV} and Sb^V chlorides with substituted oxo-organotin. The reaction of liquid sulphur trioxide with some oxo-organotin compounds were also attempted³. In this reaction the resulting products are organotin sulphate and have polymeric structures. Narula and Sharma⁴ have reported some addition compounds of oxo-organotin with chlorides of titanium(IV), ethyltin(IV) and diethyltin(IV). From this laboratory, we have already reported the addition compounds of oxo-organotin with some transition metal ions⁵. In the present work, we wish to report oxobis(tri-n-butyltin) (TBTO) compounds with Co^{II} and Ni^{II} and their spectrochemical properties.

Experimental

The metal salts used were of A.R. grade and the solvents were used after drying by usual methods. The ligand TBTO (Int Ltd., U.K.) was used as such.

Synthesis of addition compounds: All the compounds were isolated in solid state by the following general method. A solution containing the respective metal salt (0.01 mol, 25 ml methanol) and 2,2'-dimethoxypropane (15 ml) was refluxed on water-bath for ~3 h. The clear solution thus obtained was mixed with methanolic solution of ligand (0.03 mol). The reaction mixture was then stirred for ~3 h, when a coloured precipitate was slowly thrown out, which was filtered, washed with several portions of methanol and finally with ether and dried *in vacuo* over P_2O_5 . All the operations were made in inert atmosphere.

All the chemical and physical measurements were carried out as described previously⁵.

Results and Discussion

The general compositions of these compounds correspond to $M(TBTO)_4X_2$ ($M=Ni, Co$; $X=Cl, Br, I, NO_3, NCS$) and $Ni(TBTO)_6(ClO_4)_2$ (Table 1). These complexes are fairly stable at room temperature and can be stored for a long period. The complexes do not melt but decompose on heating beyond 200°. The insolubility of the compounds in all the common solvents do not permit the determination of their stereochemistry in solution state. All the complexes are very toxic and are allergic towards human skin.

Magnetism and electronic spectral studies:

Cobalt(II) complexes: The observed values of magnetic moment for the series of Co^{II} complexes of TBTO are in the range 4.2-4.7 B.M. (Table 1). These values are in agreement with those expected for tetrahedral cobalt(II) complexes⁶. Further elucidation of the stereochemistry of these complexes was made in conjunction with the spectral data.

In octahedral environment, the $\nu_1(^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow ^4T_{2g}(F))$ usually occurs in the 5500-11000 cm^{-1} region, $\nu_2(^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow ^4A_{1g}(F))$ and $\nu_3(^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow ^4T_{1g}(P), ^2G)$ are found in the 12000-17000 and 22000 cm^{-1} , respectively. In tetrahedral environment, three transitions from the ground state are expected, the first $\nu_1(^4T_g \rightarrow ^4T_g)$ is expected at the energy of 10Dq in the 3000-5000 cm^{-1} region but is not observed in most of the cases⁷. The $\nu_2(^4A_g \rightarrow ^4T_1(F))$ is usually broad and appear in the near-ir region, the $\nu_3(^4A_g \rightarrow ^4T_1(P))$ is also intense and broad and found in the 15000-20000 cm^{-1} region.

The complexes reported herein have two systems of bands lying between 6310-8330 and 16130-19000 cm^{-1} with a distribution of relative intensities between visible and near-ir bands found in tetrahedral Co^{II} complexes⁸. Since the overall spectra of these complexes are similar to other tetrahedral complexes of Co^{II} , we can assume formal tetrahedral

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL, MAGNETIC AND PARTIAL IR SPECTRAL DATA OF COBALT(II) AND NICKEL(II) COMPOUNDS OF TBTO

Compd.	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)					μ_{eff} B.M.	$\nu_{\text{Sn-O-Sn}}$ cm^{-1}	$\nu_{\text{M-O}}$ cm^{-1}
	Sn	M	O	H	X			
TBTO	—	—	—	—	—	—	788 m	—
CoCl ₂ .4TBTO	37.98 (37.80)	2.51 (2.84)	46.09 (45.86)	8.92 (8.60)	3.02 (2.82)	4.4	740 m	380 m, br
CoBr ₂ .4TBTO	36.72 (36.50)	2.15 (2.26)	44.11 (44.30)	8.44 (8.30)	6.33 (6.15)	4.5	750 m	360 w
CoI ₂ .4TBTO	35.60 (35.24)	1.99 (2.18)	42.39 (42.75)	7.82 (8.01)	9.59 (9.42)	4.7	750 m	360 w
Co(NO ₃) ₂ .4TBTO	36.81 (37.02)	2.48 (2.29)	44.75 (44.92)	8.61 (8.42)	—	4.4	760 m	370 m, br
Co(NCS) ₂ .4TBTO	36.97 (37.14)	2.48 (2.30)	46.30 (45.99)	8.72 (8.30)	4.75 (4.80)	4.42	755 m	360 m
NiCl ₂ .4TBTO	38.01 (37.81)	2.19 (2.38)	45.69 (45.87)	8.43 (8.60)	3.05 (2.82)	3.2	745 m	380 m
NiBr ₂ .4TBTO	36.35 (36.51)	2.39 (2.25)	44.19 (44.30)	8.45 (8.30)	6.02 (6.15)	3.1	760 m	360 m
NiI ₂ .4TBTO	35.41 (35.25)	2.29 (2.17)	42.92 (42.75)	8.30 (8.01)	9.61 (9.42)	2.9	750 m	360 m
Ni(ClO ₄) ₂ .6TBTO	40.02 (39.86)	1.70 (1.62)	48.24 (48.46)	9.20 (9.09)	5.80 (5.64)	3.5	760 m	380 m
Ni(NO ₃) ₂ .4TBTO	36.87 (37.03)	2.39 (2.28)	45.11 (44.92)	8.21 (8.42)	—	3.0	750 m	380 m
Ni(NCS) ₂ .4TBTO	37.33 (37.14)	2.41 (2.29)	45.88 (46.00)	8.60 (8.44)	4.27 (4.58)	3.25	760 m	370 m

stereochemistry in these cases as well. The values of $10Dq$ (4850-5570), ν_2 (7030-7898), ν_3 (16250-17670 cm^{-1}) and B' have been computed from the equations suggested by Drago. Since the complexes are distorted and spectra of the complexes involve broad bands, the absolute values of the ligand field parameters are probably not too significant. The B' values for all the complexes are of the order of 574-665 cm^{-1} , considerably reduced from the free ion value, which suggests that there is an appreciable orbital overlap. The β values range from 0.58 to 0.69.

Nickel(II) complexes: The magnetic moment values of Ni^{II}-TBTO complexes are in the range 3.2 to 3.5 B.M. (Table 1) indicating the octahedral arrangement of ligands around Ni^{II} ion in these complexes¹⁰. In general, the ligand field spectra of octahedrally surrounded Ni^{II} ion consist of three bands, ν_1 (${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}$, 7000-12000), ν_2 (${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$, 12000-20000) and ν_3 (${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$, 21000-30000 cm^{-1}). In addition, sometimes spin-forbidden transitions are also found in the 11500-15500 (ν_4) and 17000-24000 cm^{-1} regions.

The electronic spectral band positions indicate that the complexes of Ni^{II}-TBTO have octahedral geometry with slight distortion. Considering the first band, it is observed that this band is broad in all the cases with a clear indication of splitting, but it is difficult to measure visually the positions of the split bands. The first band occurs in these complexes in the 8260-8500 cm^{-1} region. This band has been assigned to ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$ (ν_1). In octahedral complexes the ν_1 band is usually taken as equal to $10Dq$. Similar splitting is shown by the second band which appears in the 14810-15925 cm^{-1} region. In some cases, as for example in Ni(TBTO)₄X₂

(X = Cl, NCS) complexes, a shoulder appears (13330 and 13350 cm^{-1}) at low energy side to the main second band. The second band has been assigned to involve the transition ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ (ν_2). The third band ν_3 usually does not show splitting but in few cases it has been found to split into two bands. In Ni(TBTO)₄Cl₂ two bands at ~26310 and 30700 cm^{-1} have been found for ν_3 , whereas in other cases only a single band in the 25640-27030 cm^{-1} region has been observed. The ν_3 band has been assigned to the transition ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$. Thus, the complexes show signs of splitting but since it is not possible to locate their exact positions they have been treated as octahedral complexes.

The spectra of these complexes yield by standard treatment, values for the ligand field parameters Dq , B' (925-995 cm^{-1}) and β (0.89-0.95). Making use of these values the energies of ν_2 and ν_3 have been calculated and checked against the observed values, since this is the justification of having cubic symmetry. The calculated values of ν_2 and ν_3 are in close agreement with the experimental values.

Infrared spectra :

The pertinent ir data for the ligand and its metal complexes have been given in Table 1. A perusal of the spectral data clearly indicates the coordination of metal ions to the ligand through the oxygen atom of the ligand. Sn-O-Sn stretching absorption in the free ligand occurs at 783 cm^{-1} which suffers a negative shift of the order 60-90 cm^{-1} on complexation indicating the metal-ligand linkage, through the oxygen atom of the Sn-O-Sn moiety^{1,2,5}. Other frequencies, such as symmetric and asymmetric ν_{CH_2} , ν_{CH_3} and ν_{CH} rocking and wagging are not much affected on complexation. Metal-oxygen stretching vibration in these complexes

has been assigned in 350-450 cm^{-1} region^{2,4,5}. Metal-chlorine stretching vibration falls in 350-310 cm^{-1} region.

In nitrate complexes the absence of ν_3 band at $\sim 1350 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ clearly indicates the absence of ionic NO_3 in the complexes. Further, the bands at 1540 (ν_4) and 1320 cm^{-1} (ν_1) are due to the splitting of ν_3 mode in the lower symmetry coordinated nitrate groups^{11,12}. Distinction between mono- and bi-dentate nitrate groups on the basis of ir spectral evidence is usually difficult, but on the basis of the separation in combination bands ($\nu_1 + \nu_4$) in 1800-1700 cm^{-1} region, the monodentate nature of the coordinated nitrate groups is concluded^{13,14}. The bands at ~ 1030 (ν_2), ~ 820 (ν_6) and $\sim 760 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (ν_3/ν_8) also appear in the spectra of the complexes due to coordinated nitrate groups. In perchlorate complex only two strong ν_3 and ν_4 absorptions are observed at ~ 1085 and 625 cm^{-1} , respectively for perchlorate ions indicating that tetrahedral symmetry has not been disturbed on complexation and all the perchlorate ions are ionic in these complexes^{15,16}. In thiocyanate complexes the three fundamental absorptions C-N stretch (ν_1), C-S stretch (ν_3) and N-C-S bending (ν_2) fall at $\sim 2045 \pm 5$, 485 ± 5 and $845 \pm 5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, respectively, which indicate that these frequencies are associated with the terminal N-bounded isothiocyanate ions¹⁷.

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